

Implementation of FinFET technology based low power 4×4 Wallace tree multiplier using hybrid full adder

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ABSTRACT

Many systems, including digital signal processors, finite impulse response (FIR) filters, application-specific integrated circuits, and microprocessors, use multipliers. The demand for low power multipliers is gradually rising day by day in the current technological trend. In this study, we describe a 4×4 Wallace multiplier based on a carry select adder (CSA) that uses less power and has a better power delay product than existing multipliers. HSPICE tool at 16 nm technology is used to simulate the results. In comparison to the traditional CSA-based multiplier, which has a power consumption of 1.7 μ W and power delay product (PDP) of 57.3 fJ, the results demonstrate that the Wallace multiplier design employing CSA with first zero finding logic (FZF) logic has the lowest power consumption of 1.4 μ W and PDP of 27.5 fJ.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In order to get a longer battery life, researchers have developed low power technologies as a result of the widespread use of portable electronic equipments. The intricacy of the design, which in turn affects battery life and device size, is heavily impacted by a tradeoff between low power and high speed [1]. Since the multiplier is used in the majority of electronic systems for real-time applications including microprocessors, finite impulse response (FIR) filters, image processing, and digital signal processing, the performance of these applications is heavily dependent on the multiplier's design [2]. It can be seen that the multiplier used for arithmetic operations like addition and multiplication contributes a significant portion of energy usage. Wallace tree multiplier is among the finest options with better power delay product (PDP) based on the currently available multipliers [3]. It is one of the options for usage in battery-operated systems because of its advantageous properties.

The Wallace tree multiplier has three stages of action. In the first stage, partial products are generated using AND gates. $N \times N$ AND gates are needed for the N -bit multiplier. Using half adders and full adders or by hybrid full adders only, parallel column bits are added in the second stage [4] until ultimately just two rows are left. This is the tree reduction stage. The second stage requires a significant amount of additional time for addition, which increases the delay. At the third stage, fast adders are used to complete the final addition of the two rows [5]. A suitable option for final addition that can be utilized to reduce the multiplier's delay is the carry select adder (CSA) [6]. Yet, using conventional CSA, a tradeoff of area can be seen. In light of this, carry select adder (CSA) with binary to excess-1 convertor (BEC-1) [7] is an additional choice for the final addition.

Different topologies can also be used for final addition, such as CSA with first zero finding logic (FZF) [8] and CSA with a combinational circuit.

The algorithm utilized by the Wallace multiplier for multiplication is described in the next section. In section 3, method for design of conventional carry select adder (CSA) based Wallace multiplier, CSA with binary to excess-1 (BEC-1) convertor based multiplier, CSA with modified BEC-1 convertor based multiplier, multiplier using CSA with FZF logic and CSA using combinational circuit based multiplier is discussed. The findings and comparison of various suggested Wallace multipliers are presented in section 4. Section 5 discusses the conclusion in detail.

2. ALGORITHM USED FOR MULTIPLICATION

The following is a basic explanation of how a Wallace tree multiplier multiplies a 4 bit number. It includes stages: stage-1 is the partial product generation stage, stage-2 is the tree reduction stage, and stage-3 is the final addition stage.

- a) Let's assume that the multiplier $b_3 b_2 b_1 b_0$ is to be applied to the multiplicand $a_3 a_2 a_1 a_0$. This can be accomplished by employing AND gates. It generates partial or multiplied products as $P_0, P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}, P_{11}, P_{12}, P_{13}, P_{14}$, and P_{15} respectively [9] shown in Table 1.
- b) The first three rows of multiplied products mentioned in Table 1. Is to be further added using hybrid full adders. This is to be done in order to reduce it into two rows shown in Table 2. Parallel addition of column bits of first three rows is done:
 - Partial product P_0 is passed directly as the least significant bit (LSB) of sum bits.
 - P_1 and P_4 is added to produce the sum bit S_0 and carry bit C_0 .
 - P_2, P_5 and P_8 is added, generating the sum bit S_1 and the carry bit C_1 .
 - Furthermore P_3, P_6 and P_9 are added, creating the sum bit as S_2 and the carry bit as C_2 .
 - Addition of P_7 and P_{10} produces the sum bit as S_3 and the carry bit as C_3 .
 - P_{11} is left for further addition.

The generated results obtained from Table 2. Tree reduction stage-2 step-1 can be expressed as partial sum bits and internal carry bits. Partial sum is generated as: $P_0 = a_0b_0, S_0 = P_1 \text{ xor } P_4, S_1 = P_2 \text{ xor } P_5 \text{ xor } P_8, S_2 = P_3 \text{ xor } P_6 \text{ xor } P_9, S_3 = P_7 \text{ xor } P_{10}, P_{11} = a_2b_3$. Internal carry is generated as C_0, C_1, C_2 and C_3 respectively. The results obtained from Table 2. Tree reduction stage-2 step-1 and fourth row in Table 1 is further added using hybrid full adders. This results in further generation of partial sum bits and partial carry bits, shown in Table 3.

The generated results obtained from Table 2. Tree reduction stage-2 step-2 can be expressed as: partial sum is generated as $P_0 = a_0b_0, S_0 = P_1 \text{ xor } P_4, S_4 = S_1 \text{ xor } C_0, S_5 = S_2 \text{ xor } C_1 \text{ xor } a_3b_0, S_5 = S_2 \text{ xor } C_1 \text{ xor } a_3b_0, S_6 = S_3 \text{ xor } C_2 \text{ xor } a_3b_1, S_7 = a_2b_3 \text{ xor } C_3 \text{ xor } a_3b_2$ and $P_{15} = a_3b_3$. Internal carry is generated as C_4, C_5, C_6 and C_7 respectively.

- c) The final addition of the last two rows uses any fast adder [10]. In the proposed work, carry select adder is used for final addition. The final generated result being sum bits beginning with the LSB and an most significant bit (MSB) bit serving as the carry bit shown in Table 4 as final addition stage-3.

Table 1. Partial product generation stage-1

Generated partial product						Row	
			$P_3 = a_0 \text{ AND } b_3 = a_0b_3$	$P_2 = a_0 \text{ AND } b_2 = a_0b_2$	$P_1 = a_0 \text{ AND } b_1 = a_0b_1$	$P_0 = a_0 \text{ AND } b_0 = a_0b_0$	1
		$P_7 = a_1 \text{ AND } b_3 = a_1b_3$	$P_6 = a_1 \text{ AND } b_2 = a_1b_2$	$P_5 = a_1 \text{ AND } b_1 = a_1b_1$	$P_4 = a_1 \text{ AND } b_0 = a_1b_0$		2
	$P_{11} = a_2 \text{ AND } b_3 = a_2b_3$	$P_{10} = a_2 \text{ AND } b_2 = a_2b_2$	$P_9 = a_2 \text{ AND } b_1 = a_2b_1$	$P_8 = a_2 \text{ AND } b_0 = a_2b_0$			3
$P_{15} = a_3 \text{ AND } b_3 = a_3b_3$	$P_{14} = a_3 \text{ AND } b_2 = a_3b_2$	$P_{13} = a_3 \text{ AND } b_1 = a_3b_1$	$P_{12} = a_3 \text{ AND } b_0 = a_3b_0$				4

Table 2. Tree reduction stage-2 step-1

Tree reduction-step 1					
$P_{11} = a_2b_3$	$S_3 = P_7+P_{10}$	$S_2 = P_3+P_6+P_9$	$S_1 = P_2+P_5+P_8$	$S_0 = P_1+P_4$	$P_0 = a_0b_0$
C_3	C_2	C_1	C_0		

The result generated with the final sum bits and output carry bit is expressed as: $P_0 = a_0b_0, S_0 = P_1 \text{ xor } P_4, S_4 = S_1 \text{ xor } C_0, S_8 = S_5 \text{ xor } C_4, S_9 = S_6 \text{ xor } C_5 \text{ xor } C_8, S_{10} = S_7 \text{ xor } C_6 \text{ xor } C_9$ and $S_{11} = P_{15} \text{ xor } C_7 \text{ xor } C_{10}$. Internal carry is generated as C_8, C_9, C_{10} and final output carry is C_{11} respectively.

Table 3. Tree reduction stage-2 step-2

Tree Reduction-step 2 using half adder and full adders							
Result obtained for addition of first three rows		a2b3	S3	S2	S1	S0	P0 = a0b0
		C3	C2	C1	C0		
Fourth row	a3b3	a3b2	a3b1	a3b0			
Generated partial sum bits	P15 = a3b3	S7	S6	S5	S4	S0	P0 = a0b0
Generated partial carry bit	C7	C6	C5	C4			

Table 4. Final addition stage-3

Final addition stage using half adder and full adders							
	P15 = a3b3	S7	S6	S5	S4	S0	P0 = a0b0
	C7	C6	C5	C4			
	C10	C9	C8				
Generated final sum bits	S11	S10	S9	S8	S4	S0	P0 = a0b0
Generated final carry bit	C11 (cout)						

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Wallace multiplier using conventional carry select adder-WM-design 1

Wallace multiplier (WM)-design 1 consists of three stages as mentioned in the algorithm and is shown in Figure 1. The first two stages are designed using hybrid full adders only. Half adders used in conventional Wallace multiplier is replaced with hybrid full adder. Partial products generated in stage 1 are fed into stage 2, except P0 = a0b0. P0 is passed directly as least significant output sum bit. The output of stage 2 is fed as input into stage 3 for final addition. Output bits S0, S4, S8 obtained from stage-2 are also passed directly as output bits. In stage-3, carry select adder [11] is chosen for addition at the final stage. The design inside red color dotted line shown in the figure is the carry select adder which consists of two stage ripple carry adder. Ripple carry adder is designed using hybrid full adder [12]-[13] each consisting of 22 transistors.

Figure 1. WM-design-1

3.2. Wallace multiplier using BEC-1 based carry select adder-WM-design 2

In WM-design 2 shown in Figure 2, a modification is done in WM-design 1. Here, conventional carry select adder used in final addition stage-3 is replaced by BEC-1 converter based carry select adder. It consists of less number of logic gates [14], [15] which further results in low area utilization and low power consumption in comparison to the conventional carry select adder based multiplier [16]-[19]. BEC-1 logic circuit consists of inverter, XOR gates and AND gate. The circuit shown in the figure with the red dotted line is BEC-1 circuit. The output of the BEC-1 circuit is obtained through the multiplexer with C9 as the select line. Sum bit S10, S11 and carry output bit C11 is the output of the multiplexer. Other output bits are generated from stage-1 and stage-2 respectively.

Figure 2. WM-design 2

3.3. Wallace multiplier using modified BEC-1 based CSA-WM-design 3

In order to further minimize logic gates in the carry propagation path [20]-[23] for the proposed WM-design 2, modified BEC-1 based CSA logic circuit is proposed for Wallace multiplier, WM-design 3 shown in Figure 3. We know that, the most significant output carry bit of the multiplier output is generated in the carry propagation path. Replacement of XOR gate with OR gate in the existing BEC-1 circuit discussed in WM-design 2, simplifies the logic function in the carry propagation path [24].

The major goal of the design is to minimise the number of basic logic gates at the most significant bit (MSB) position on the carry propagation path by considering all feasible input scenarios. Hence, minimizing area, and power consumption. In addition to this, the output obtain through the OR gate is exactly same as obtained through XOR gate in case of BEC-1 circuit used in WM-design 2. S_{10} and S_{11} bit of the result is generated using multiplexer shown in red colour dotted block in Figure 2. The output carry bit c_{out} (C_{11}) is generated using OR gate. $P_0 = a_0b_0$, S_0, S_4, S_8 and S_9 are generated using other two stages i.e., stage-1 and stage-2 respectively.

3.4. Wallace multiplier using FZF logic based CSA-WM-design 4

In WM-design 4 shown in Figure 4, for final addition stage, FZF circuit replaces second stage ripple carry adder and multiplexers present in conventional CSA based multiplier. FZF design helps in reducing area utilization and power consumption. S_{10}, S_{11} and c_{out} (C_{11}) is the output through XOR gate of FZF logic circuit. Other output bits obtained through hybrid full adder are S_8, S_4, S_0 and LSB output bit a_0b_0 .

3.5. Wallace multiplier using D latch based CSA-WM-design 5

In the proposed WM-design 5 shown in Figure 5, the second stage of carry select adder in the final addition stage of Wallace multiplier is replaced by a parallel structure of D latch [10]. D latch is used to store one bit of information with enable pin as a clock. Output is stored in D latch for enable pin = 1 and when it goes low $en = 0$, D latch output and hybrid full adder sum bit output is sent to the multiplexer.

Using a proper select line as a internal carry bit output (C8) from previous hybrid full adder, multiplexer output [25] is obtained as S9, S10 and S11 output sum bit and cout (C11) output carry bit. Other output bits are generated using hybrid full adders in the first two stages respectively.

Figure 3. WM-design 3

Figure 4. WM-design 4

Figure 5. WM-design 5

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simulation is done using synopsys HSPICE tool at 16 nm FinFeT technology node. Predictive technology model multi gate (PTM-MG) library is used in order to obtain the results. Transient analysis is done in order to verify the output results. Average propagation delay, average power consumption, PDP and energy delay product (EDP) is calculated for the different proposed designs. Results are calculated for three different cases so that analysis of the circuits can be done at three extreme conditions. The three different cases for which the proposed designs are simulated is shown in Table 5.

Table 6 shows the results obtained for proposed Wallace multiplier designs viz. WM-design 1, WM-design 2, WM-design 3, WM-design 4, and WM-design 5 at room temperature. The supply voltage is 0.8 V. Parameters such as delay, power, PDP, and EDP is calculated for various designs.

Table 7 shows the results obtained for proposed Wallace multiplier designs viz. WM-design 1, WM-design 2, WM-design 3, WM-design 4, and WM-design 5 at a temperature = -40 °C. The supply voltage is 0.9 V. Parameters such as delay, power, PDP, and EDP is calculated for various designs.

Table 8 shows the results obtained for proposed Wallace multiplier designs viz. WM-design 1, WM-design 2, WM-design 3, WM-design 4, and WM-design 5 at a temperature = 120 °C. The supply voltage is 0.7 V. Parameters such as delay, power, PDP, and EDP is calculated for various designs.

Table 9 shows the comparative analysis of the proposed Wallace multiplier designs viz. WM-design 1, WM-design 2, WM-design 3, WM-design 4, and WM-design 5 with the existing multipliers. Average power consumption of the proposed designs is compared with the existing designs. Proposed designs shows better results with respect to the existing one.

Table 5. Cases for simulation results

Case	Supply voltage	Temperature
1	0.8V	25 °C
2	0.9V	-40 °C
3	0.7V	120 °C

Table 6. Case 1, simulated results obtained with supply voltage = 0.8 V and temperature = 25 °C

Proposed design	Delay (ns)	Power (μW)	PDP (fJ)	EDP (fJ-ns)
WM-design 1	34.5	1.7	57.3	1976.9
WM-design 2	44.5	1.5	66.3	2950.4
WM-design 3	25.1	1.5	36.9	926.2
WM-design 4	20.2	1.4	27.5	555.5
WM-design 5	54.8	1.6	85.5	4685.4

Table 7. Case 2, simulated results obtained with supply voltage = 0.9 V and temperature = -40 °C

Proposed design	Delay (ns)	Power (μ W)	PDP (fJ)	EDP (fJ-ns)
WM-design 1	14.7	11.4	167.6	2462.3
WM-design 2	15.3	2.4	36.9	564.2
WM-design 3	29.4	2.4	69.1	2031.2
WM-design 4	20.2	2.2	44.0	889.5
WM-design 5	34.6	2.6	89.6	3100.6

Table 8. Case 3, simulated results obtained with supply voltage = 0.7 V and temperature = 120 °C

Proposed design	Delay (ns)	Power (μ W)	PDP (fJ)	EDP (fJ-ns)
WM-design 1	34.7	1.1	38.1	1322.1
WM-design 2	44	0.93	40.9	1799.6
WM-design 3	29.8	0.75	22.3	664.54
WM-design 4	24.4	0.86	20.9	509.96
WM-design 5	54.6	0.96	52.5	2866.5

Table 9. Comparative analysis of the proposed designs with the existing work

Wallace multiplier	Power (mW)
[7]-conventional	83.22
[7]-using CSLA	82.88
[7]-using CSLA with BEC	80.98
[12]	0.694
[13]	0.54
[14]	0.082
[15]	0.192
WM-design 1-proposed	0.0017
WM-design 2-proposed	0.0015
WM-design 3-proposed	0.0015
WM-design 4-proposed	0.0014
WM-design 5-proposed	0.0016

5. CONCLUSION

Multipliers are used for many applications such as in biomedical signal processing, portable electronic equipment. In this paper, various designs are proposed for the Wallace multiplier having low power consumption and improved PDP. It is concluded that Wallace multiplier (WM-design 4) designed using FZF based CSA shows better results in comparison to the other proposed designs. WM-design 4 has a PDP of 27.5 fJ which is 52% less and EDP of 555.5 fJ-ns which is 71.9% less than conventional CSA based Wallace multiplier (WM-design 1). However, Wallace multiplier (WM-design 2) designed using BEC-1 based CSA and Wallace multiplier (WM-design 4) designed using D latch based CSA has more PDP and EDP in comparison to the other proposed designs.

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